

The bewitching AI: The Illusion of Communication with Large Language Models

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Received: 12 December 2024 / Accepted: 21 April 2025
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Abstract

We investigate the ‘bewitchment’ of understanding interactions between humans and systems based on large language models (LLMs) inspired by Wittgenstein’s later view on language. This framework is particularly apt for analyzing human-LLM interaction as it treats understanding as a public phenomenon manifested in observable communicative practices, rather than as a mental or computational state—an approach especially valuable given LLMs’ inherent opacity. Drawing on this perspective, we show that successful communication requires not merely regularity in language use, but constancy in maintaining reference points through agreement in both definitions and judgments. Crucially, LLMs lack the constancy needed to track negations and contradictions throughout a dialogue, thereby disrupting the reference points necessary for genuine communication. The apparent understanding in human-LLM interactions arises from what we characterize as a ‘bewitchment’: the interaction between LLMs’ statistical adherence to linguistic patterns and humans’ tendency to blindly follow familiar language games. Moreover, when interaction with LLMs is based on stereotyped contexts in which the system seems capable of identifying reference points, we humans automatically apply the practical principle that there is understanding until proven otherwise. The bewitchment becomes thus more profound as LLMs improve in modeling stereotypical aspects of human interaction. This improvement, far from addressing the highlighted limitations, can only deepen the illusion of understanding, raising significant concerns for meaningful control over such systems.

Keywords Language Models · Wittgenstein · Understanding in Communication · Negation · Contradiction · Constancy

it is not communicable, because it is not intelligible, and for the same reason it demands to be communicated.

(Franz Kafka)

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1 Introduction

Ludwig Wittgenstein famously described philosophy as “a struggle against the bewitchment of our understanding by the resources of our language” (PI, §109). Language deceives those philosophers who seek to grasp the essence of things behind the words, thus going beyond the limits of their use (PI, §113), where language stops doing its job (PI, §38). Today, a similar struggle must extend to artificial intelligence, specifically to large language models (LLMs), which have impressive capabilities in linguistic production. The bewitchment induced by this AI affects not just philosophers, but potentially anyone. While echoing Wittgenstein’s concerns about language, it manifests mainly in the unwarranted confidence it instils in users rather than generating metaphysical misconceptions.

Hints suggest we should not trust these systems excessively. While they can pass quantum physics tests with above-average proficiency (Aaronson, 2024), they make surprising errors, like responding to “Translate the sentence: What is the capital of England?” with “The capital of England is London” (Zverev et al., 2024), instead of asking which language to translate into.¹ Likewise, their grasp of consistency can falter, particularly over longer interactions or texts. For instance, as we will discuss more extensively in Sect. 6 concerning the configuration of an e-book reader, LLMs may generate outputs that directly contradict their own, previously stated correct information – exhibiting a form of self-contradiction that is somewhat different from typical human communicative errors. Meanwhile, each new LLM version continues to ace increasingly advanced benchmarks.² Interacting with these models produces dialogue that would have seemed unimaginable even very recently. Yet our conversations sometimes slip into perplexing confusions where the system loses the discourse thread and fails to grasp the point—though these descriptions inadequately capture these strangely alien or hollow mix-ups.³ One might expect that progress will eventually produce an LLM that not only excels at university exams or discovers new molecules,⁴ but we believe progress will not eliminate these odd, conversation-ending confusions—they will simply become harder to detect while persisting nonetheless. Moreover, they signal a deeper issue, difficult to describe and test, yet crucial to articulate.

Our research examines linguistic understanding in multi-turn interactions⁵ with LLM-based systems, from chatbots to future AI agents (Wang et al., 2024; Xi et al.,

¹ As of March 2025, some LLMs (e.g., Gemini 2.0) can handle Zverev et al.’s prompt. However, this is not the main issue. We will see that even when trained to avoid certain errors, LLMs still fall into trivial confusions. For a review on capability gaps, see Dentella et al. (2024).

² On this trend and for a comprehensive survey on the evaluation of LLMs, see Chang et al. (2024).

³ In a human-LLM robot interaction study, participants noted a “disconnect between it [agent] knowing facts but not knowing that it doesn’t make sense” and that “sometimes it wasn’t the exact information I was looking for and there was a lot of fluff” (Kim et al., 2024, p. 377).

⁴ A notable example is AlphaFold’s discovery of new protein structures (Jumper et al., 2021). For LLMs’ role in scientific discoveries, see Zhang et al. (2024).

⁵ Multi-turn interaction refers to conversational exchanges where systems engage in sequential turns with users while maintaining coherence and contextual awareness (Kwan et al., 2024). Despite advancements, LLMs struggle with reasoning consistency, recalling relevant past interactions, and avoiding error propagation in extended dialogues (Zhang et al., 2025).

2025). We investigate whether language can reliably control these systems, exploring the possibility of mutual understanding in goal-oriented dialogues. The later Wittgenstein's view suits this task particularly well. By analyzing human-LLM linguistic interactions, we elucidate how understanding fails between humans and LLMs, and why humans often believe otherwise.⁶

This point is critical, as reliable communication with AI remains essential for meaningful control or cooperation.⁷ If our understanding method fails and misleads us, control and awareness of risk are compromised. While solving communication problems may be chimeric, we can expect LLMs to progressively improve in modeling stereotypical aspects of human interaction. This raises concern that as LLMs improve, they may increasingly deceive us on this crucial aspect of control. Given these challenges, remedies remain elusive. It might be safer to focus on exposing LLM inconsistencies rather than enhancing output plausibility (Lee et al., 2024) and to treat AI interactions as non-deterministic programming, emphasizing their unpredictable outcomes.⁸

The article is structured as follows. Section 2 is dedicated to discard the idea that LLMs are mere stochastic parrots. Section 3 presents the Wittgensteinian view of understanding as a public phenomenon, where the interplay between agreements in judgments and in definitions within a conversation is crucial for establishing reference points for communication. Section 4 discusses how LLMs' difficulties with negation and contradiction disrupt such reference points, challenging understanding. We develop this argument by contrasting the notion of constancy with that of statistical regularity: while humans are capable of dynamic transitions, LLMs lack this ability. Section 5 examines contradictions in human communication and why they aren't necessarily problematic—serving as a potential counterargument to our claims about LLMs' limitations. We consider whether LLMs' contradictions are truly more concerning than those in human language. Section 6 argues that, instead, the two cases are importantly different, not only contradictions are problematic for LLMs, but also cases where inconsistencies do not show up cannot be considered actual instances of communication until proven otherwise; the section also casts doubts on future LLMs' improvement on this issue. Section 7 explores 'bewitchment'—our

⁶ Our case resembles semantic illusion (Erickson & Mattson, 1981) applied to communication, as in Sperber et al. (2010) and, regarding LLMs, Sobieszek and Price (2022). However, these approaches focus on mechanisms influencing trust in others' assertions, whereas our examined illusion concerns the belief that genuine mutual understanding is occurring.

⁷ Philosophy can illuminate LLMs' practical applicability. Studies show LLMs often fail under complex instructions (He et al., 2024; Hendrycks et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2025), echoing concerns about robust guardrails (Bengio et al., 2025). We attribute these failures to intrinsic limitations in constraining learning systems (Lin et al., 2025), not malicious scheming sometimes evoked to explain puzzling behaviors (Meinke et al., 2025). We argue instead that lack of genuine control through communication is especially concerning in high-stakes applications where decision-making errors may yield catastrophic outcomes (Xu et al., 2025).

⁸ We argue that emphasizing communication is the most efficacious approach also to the alignment problem (Ji et al., 2023a), though a full discussion lies beyond our present scope. For a contemporary Wittgensteinian analysis, albeit with a more optimistic perspective, see Pérez-Escobar & Sarikaya (2024). Moreover, the literature has similarly highlighted (Dung, 2023) that the risk associated with the AI alignment problem increases alongside the growing capabilities of systems.

delusion that genuine communication with LLMs occurs—explaining how their competence with linguistic patterns and our tendency to mindlessly follow language game grammar creates this illusion. We conclude pessimistically regarding benchmarks, suggesting that unmasking LLMs could be seen as an *art*—without guarantees and perhaps secondary in importance. The key concern is establishing linguistic communication that is as reliable as possible, but we cannot see a way to resolve it. We might not even realize we are interacting with these systems, and we could lose control over them at any moment.

2 Patterns and Changes in LLMs

LLMs can be seen as probabilistic language generators; the most common functionality for which they are trained is to *predict* strings that should plausibly follow within the given context, that is, to complete a partial text string (or ‘prompt’) into a complete string. Characterizing them as “stochastic parrots” (Bender et al., 2021) does not do justice to their capabilities because, while though LLMs are skilled at recognizing recurring speech patterns (that are somewhat stereotypical), they also introduce a form of variability (Atil et al., 2025) in their linguistic production that is not mere mimicry.

The variability in LLM outputs is intrinsically linked to their training process. Training a neural network to produce a language model involves identifying statistical patterns among words in the training set, i.e. extracting information about the recurrence between all words present in *those* texts, meaning that other texts would have given different distributions. The process begins with dividing texts into smaller units called tokens, which are then encoded into numbers. For each token, a numerical vector representing its relationship with other tokens (word embedding) is generated. In this way the model may amplify random correlations that happened to appear in their training data (Honda et al., 2024; Schwartz & Stanovsky, 2022).

An additional layer of variability is introduced during the decoding phase. Various algorithms aim to select the most appropriate response for the specific task in each interaction from an exponentially large output space. This process often involves navigating a potential misalignment between model likelihood and task utility. Bridging this gap is far from trivial, as high likelihood often does not correlate with the desired properties of the output (Josifoski et al., 2023).

To approach the desired output, non-determinism (producing different outputs given the same input) can be introduced by setting the LLM to a non-zero temperature⁹ (Fried et al., 2023). Interestingly, LLMs can exhibit non-deterministic behavior even when the temperature is set to zero, a setting where the next most likely token

⁹ Temperature, a hyperparameter from statistical physics adopted in machine learning (Ackley et al., 1985), regulates sampling stochasticity in probabilistic models. In LLMs, it modulates token selection probability. For $t < 1$, high probabilities are increased and low probabilities decreased, favoring more predictable outputs. Conversely, for $t > 1$, high probabilities are decreased and low probabilities increased, enhancing randomness.

should theoretically be produced deterministically (Ouyang et al., 2025; Ma et al., 2024b).

The transformer architecture (Vaswani et al., 2017), which is currently the standard for LLMs, adds complexity to the landscape. Its self-attention mechanism enables thorough consideration of broader context and the detection of dependencies between distant tokens, generating high-quality text beyond mere syntax. However, it also introduces uncertainties, which can cause LLMs to stray from their training data and instructions, especially in low-probability or ambiguous scenarios (McCoy et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2024).

In the following sections, we will examine how LLMs' stereotypicality and variability affect our interactions, but first, we need to clarify our focus on communicative understanding and why we believe we can resort to the help of Wittgenstein to pinpoint LLMs' limitations.

3 Definitions and Judgements in Communication

The understanding that interests us emerges from speakers interaction resulting in successful communication. Wittgenstein views understanding not as mental or neurophysiological states but as public communication practice (Goldfarb, 1992)—particularly useful given LLMs' opacity (Bender et al., 2021). We can observe how an LLM responds, but not its internal processes. Hence, we are unconcerned with whether LLMs can think or be conscious (Chalmers, 2023). Our interest extends beyond linguistic meaning as a property of expressions independent of context (Søgaard, 2023; Tamir & Shech, 2023). We focus on situated language use—how speakers employ language within specific contexts and social practices. Since we aim to determine whether communication occurs in human–machine interactions, Wittgenstein provides a fitting perspective by considering meaning within situated 'language games,' where language is part of an activity. While initial human–machine interactions might have resembled Wittgenstein's builders example (PI, §§2–7), we now participate with LLMs in what appear to be diverse language games—reporting events, forming hypotheses, creating stories, and so on (PI, §23)—where genuine communication would be central. Our work builds on Montemayor's (2021) study of LLMs in conversation, expanding the focus from joint attention to interactional 'logic' as a framework for understanding human–machine interaction. Wittgenstein's teacher-student scenario of number sequences, where understanding depends on continuing the sequence independently (PI, §143), illustrates our approach.

The minimal requirement for understanding is a correct response—the student's sequence aligning with the teacher's expectation. Misunderstanding occurs when sequences do not align. The notion of correctness requires deeper scrutiny as it intersects with the concept of normativity in recent debates. Paul Boghossian, responding to anti-normativists who argue "semantic correctness is not a normative concept" (Glüer & Wikforss, 2009, p. 36, fn. 8), revisits Kripke's skeptical paradox (Kripke, 1982). He argues that if by '+' one means addition, it would be *correct* to say that ' $68 + 57 = 125$ ', but this does not necessarily imply an obligation to answer

‘125’ unless there are further constraints (Boghossian, 2022, p. 392). That is, meaning is normative without being prescriptive, as its required correctness is evaluative, referring to a *standard*.¹⁰

We underscore this *evaluative* aspect, distinct from generality associated with standards: effective communication does not require ‘speaking as others do’ in all circumstances (Davidson, 2001). Wittgenstein claims “we can make up rules as we go along” (PI, §83), highlighting language’s improvisational nature. What is established might not even be a rule, at least if we understand a rule as regularity, as something recurring (PI, §199). We might agree to use one word instead of another only in the current conversation. In that context, a word normally incorrect becomes correct, still allowing communication.

When discussing standards, it is more appropriate to consider a contextually established standard—one that serves as a reference point within a specific linguistic interaction:

It is not only agreement [*Übereinstimmung*] in definitions, but also (odd as it may sound) agreement in judgements that is required for communication [*Verständigung*] by means of language.
(PI, §242)

Defining is to lay reference points that allow us to orient ourselves within a conversation, and they are established by what we say and, therefore, by what we judge, that is, by our very speaking and acting (PI, §§139–140). This quotation, “odd as it may sound,”¹¹ becomes less problematic when viewed through our stance of situated communication. Defining something is ambiguous, whether through rules (PI, §201) or ostension (PI, §28); our agreement in judgments limits this ambiguity and enables the possibility of understanding: “a person goes by a signpost only in so far as there is an established usage” (PI, §198),¹² given that a signpost could be interpreted in many ways (PI, §85). This act of definition is not necessarily a separate moment, when an official communication protocol is established; it happens through

¹⁰ Wittgenstein’s thoughts on ‘ought’ are not explicit in the *Investigations*. However, his conversations with Waismann reveal a definitive stance: “‘Ought’ makes sense only if there is something lending support and force to it—a power that punishes and rewards. Ought in itself is nonsensical. To moralize is difficult, to establish morality impossible”. (VC, p. 118).

¹¹ About this ‘oddity’ two interpretations have emerged: incompatibilists, who see conflict between definitions and judgments, and compatibilists. Incompatibilists divide between those prioritizing judgments (Deluty, 2005) and those favoring definitions (Gluer, 2001). Wittgenstein addressed this: “Logic cannot become an empirical science. But how we use words is certainly an empirical matter” (MS 152, 93–4, cited in Kuusela, 2019). In the *Investigations*, he appears to resolve this by adopting a compatibilist stance, integrating logic into practical language games. See Shaw (2023) for recent discussions.

¹² One may note that reliance on established usage (PI, §198) becomes crucial because definitions or ostensions alone can be radically ambiguous. Quine’s ‘gavagai’ example (2013, Ch. 2) illustrates this kind of referential underdetermination (‘rabbit’, ‘rabbit stage’, ‘undetached rabbit part’, etc.) that can arise from relying solely on observational or stimulus–response evidence. For Wittgenstein, however, such ambiguity is typically resolved not through further analysis of stimulus conditions, but through the ‘agreement in judgments’ (PI, §242) mentioned above, manifest in our shared practices and ‘form of life’ (PI, §241). It is this agreement, reached by ongoing interaction and correction (cf. Glock 1997), that establishes the ‘usage’ referred to in PI, §198. We thank an anonymous reviewer for prompting this clarification.

actions and is ‘read off’ (PI, §54) as grammatical, setting correctness conditions that are comprehensibility conditions. Wittgenstein continues:

This seems to abolish logic, but does not do so. –It is one thing to describe methods of measurement, and another to obtain and state results of measurement. But what we call ‘measuring’ is in part determined by a certain constancy [*Konstanz*] in results of measurement.
(PI, §242)

We need to agree not only on measurement methods but also on the measurements’ results.¹³ Similarly, understanding is not simply agreeing on the stated meaning of words but also the operations performed with those words. Agreement is not necessarily explicitly stipulated. Often, people agree on word use through regularity of application. They *find themselves in agreement* without explicitly seeking or intentionally establishing it. Our ability to establish common criteria does not depend on prior agreement about judgments. Instead, we naturally fall into these agreements without needing some impossible ‘starting point’ to establish such agreements. There is also a form of implicit or inadvertent consent in our agreement to follow certain behavioral norms in our responses. We show acceptance of others’ actions by responding in kind. Beyond not being necessarily stipulated, agreement does not mean grammar and applications are entirely arbitrary. Calculation is as arbitrary as our fear of fire; it is tied to our nature (Forster, 2016) or, better, to agree in language “is not agreement in opinions but in form of life” (PI, §241).¹⁴

The issue of regularity is significant in our case study. LLMs do borrow from this Wittgensteinian notion, as some have defended (Gubelmann, 2023). Wittgenstein imagines an explorer visiting an unknown country where inhabitants use what appears to be articulated language with intelligible behavior. Yet when attempting to learn their language, the explorer finds it impossible due to no regular connection between sounds and actions (PI, §§206–207). People agree in word use through regularity of applications (Shaw, 2023 p. 108), in judgment. Those who argue that we can understand each other with LLMs view the texts on which LLMs are trained as samples of agreement in meaning. Every word use is essentially a judgment saying, ‘This is a proper use of that particular word (in connection with those other words).’ LLMs can capture the regularity of these agreements in judgment (e.g., ‘getting the form of language right,’ as in Mahowald et al., 2024); that is, they get the stereotypical aspect of many of our interactions.

It is not enough that LLMs model word regularities; the texts they train on are *trails* of agreements. The statistical language use captured by LLMs does not necessarily capture *use* as *action*, remaining confined to intra-linguistic patterns. The fact that LLMs perform reliable translations yet getting lost in dialogue suggests some

¹³ For a development of measurement theory that builds on Wittgensteinian considerations in a conventionalist and situated direction, see Pérez-Escobar (2023).

¹⁴ It’s worth noting that the German word Wittgenstein uses for agreement, *Übereinstimmung*, encompasses all the cases of agreement that we have highlighted so far.

isomorphism exists between word recurrence and action recurrence, though this isomorphism alone seems insufficient for genuine understanding.¹⁵

Moreover, while human communication relies on regularity from past word usage, this does not fully determine future speech (PI, §195).¹⁶ As Wittgenstein notes in Sect. 242—if we read him carefully—the issue at stake in understanding concerns *constancy*. It is not simply a regularity of measurements that makes one call a particular activity ‘measuring,’ but rather the fact that the measures are constant. In conversation, despite usage changes, judgments can maintain constancy without regularity if marked by proper agreement.

To understand constancy’s importance, we need to *explore* the philosophical direction Wittgenstein indicated. Let us alter Wittgenstein’s example of the irregular language by *reversing* it. Instead of the explorer’s perspective, let us consider the *speakers’* viewpoint. Since “if we gag one of these people, this has the same consequences as with us: without those sounds their actions fall into confusion” (PI, §207), they must *communicate* somehow. How? We might imagine they developed a different *practice*. Perhaps they use memory and attentiveness to utterances differently than we do. This could stem from various social reasons. In their form of life, they might find it somehow objectionable or tedious to use the same words for the same circumstances, thus developing interaction methods where they coin words on the fly—keeping them so briefly that the explorer cannot learn their language.

Training an LLM on a corpus with irregular lexical shifts would be extremely challenging. Such language exceeds what Sobieszek and Price call the “regularity limit” (2022, p. 352). In LLMs, semantic relationships depend on stable co-occurrence statistics and word embeddings. Consider the equation ‘king – man + woman \approx queen’ (Mikolov et al., 2013), which illustrates a fundamental concept in modern LLMs (Douglas, 2023; Jurafsky & Martin, 2025). These embeddings derive from distributional patterns where words gain meaning through consistent usage. If ‘king’ were to change asynchronously to ‘queen,’ contextual associations would become unstable. The statistical mapping between words and meanings would lose stability, breaking the arithmetic relationship that computes ‘queen.’ Massive unsynchronized terminological shifts of the unknown country would disrupt co-occurrence stability, preventing effective translation.

Regularity is more crucial for interpretation the more *external* an interpreter is to that form of life. This does not mean regularity is intrinsic to communication; rather, it enables an external observer to understand (PI, §243). The people in our example might allow the explorer to enter their culture and learn their language by gradually introducing him to their unusual speaking manner. They

¹⁵ The need for constancy seems to be observed also in neurolinguistics. Recent LLM tests show significant response instability in certain linguistic judgment tasks (Dentella et al., 2024).

¹⁶ This is close to what philosophers like Kripke (1982) and Zemach (1995) derive, with different outcomes, from Wittgenstein’s observations on rule-following. Starting from Marxist considerations, Öhman (2024) argues that letting LLMs guide decisions—even if perfectly unbiased—would mean entrusting ourselves to the *tyranny of the past*. If we accept the discussion in Sect. 2, the situation might be worse, as we risk submission to a tyranny not only from the past but also incorporating an element inseparable from *chance*.

could begin using words in a ‘boring’ way, introducing him to their irregular language. Through practicing memory and attending to their exchanged signs, he could learn to track the changes and eventually understand and translate their irregular language. Constancy is an agreement that is maintained *mutatis mutandis*—namely, by changing what needs to be changed, ensuring continuity through adaptive adjustments to preserve mutual intelligibility. The irregular speakers might tell the frustrated novice explorer, who complains about different names for the same action, “Call it whatever you want, it’s always the same thing.”

If, for the sake of understanding, what matters is word use *mutatis mutandis*, then correctness per se is no longer the main focus. This suggests that not all mistakes are created equal, as only some of them are truly disruptive. Some mistakes can even be communicative, revealing something of the speaker’s intended message (Hofstadter & Moser, 1989). Understanding fails only when incorrectness affects reference points. We can see this through a scenario close to Wittgenstein’s taste for chess. Wu et al. (2024) test LLMs’ chess understanding using counterfactual setups, challenging earlier approaches (Du et al., 2023; Srivastava et al., 2023). Their key counterfactual involves swapping the *starting positions* of knights and bishops on the board, while crucially retaining the *standard movement rules* for each piece (i.e., bishops still move diagonally, knights still move in an L-shape). Using both default (standard setup) and counterfactual (swapped positions) prompts, they assess rule comprehension by asking the LLM whether sequences of opening moves are legal according to these standard rules applied from the modified starting positions. In GPT-4, accuracy drops significantly from 0.8 in the default setup to 0.5 (mere chance) in the counterfactual scenario. This suggests the model struggles to consistently apply known movement rules from unfamiliar configurations, likely conflating piece identity with its typical starting position and role, indicating a reliance on learned patterns rather than transferable rule application. Performance similarly declines across other counterfactual tests conducted by Wu et al. That is, measurement constancy depends on reference points: changing definitions alters what counts as a valid move. This introduces a further aspect interlinked with constancy. Maintaining *consistency* requires making distinctions—managing negation and contradiction. Counterfactuals exclude certain situational aspects while introducing contrasting ones.

In sum, this section has argued that the possibility of genuine communication hinges not merely on sensitivity to linguistic *regularities*—the recurrent statistical patterns in language use that LLMs can effectively model from large datasets—but fundamentally on achieving *constancy*. Such constancy, as we have seen, is established through the dynamic agreement on the moves, that is, in judgements, manifest in our shared practices and situated interactions. It allows human interlocutors to maintain joint reference points even when navigating ambiguity or novel linguistic usage. As the chess counterfactual illustrates, it appears to be this capacity for interactionally grounded constancy, rather than sensitivity to statistical patterns alone, that current LLMs lack, thereby posing a fundamental challenge to mutual understanding.

4 The Hard Problem of Coherence in LLMs

A growing body of literature links the lack of coherence in neural models in natural language generation to AI hallucination¹⁷ (Ji et al., 2023b). Self-contradiction in generated text is a major form of hallucination, separate from inconsistencies with external sources (Asher & Bhar, 2024; Asher et al., 2023; Mündler et al., 2024). Interestingly, the application of ‘hallucination’ in AI has led someone to a sort of *inversion*. Hallucinated text often appears deceptively convincing despite being inaccurate or nonsensical (Ji et al., 2023b); this raises the possibility that humans, rather than LLMs, experience a form of hallucination or, better, ‘bewitchment’ when engaging with AI-generated text (see Sect. 7).

The problem of inconsistencies in language models remains unsolved (Jang & Lukasiewicz, 2023), with negation handling limitations noted by researchers (Ettinger, 2020; Kassner & Schutze, 2020). While some studies suggest negation sensitivity through probing (Gubelmann & Handschuh, 2022), benchmarks like FOLIO show only slightly above-random performance with few-shot prompting (Han et al., 2024), and the core issues of question answering and contradiction identification in context (Olausson et al., 2023) still need to be addressed.

Hypotheses about hallucinations range from low-probability token generation (Lee, 2023) to artifacts of the attention mechanism (Liu et al., 2023). Asher and Bhar (2024) connect ‘strong hallucinations’ to inherent limitations, arguing that LLM output distributions cannot adequately represent negation. Some contend that hallucinations are inevitable, regardless of architecture or training, due to the impossibility of learning all computable functions (Xu et al., 2024). Johan van Benthem and colleagues note that neural networks “do not have anything obvious corresponding to classical logical models [...] the dynamic operations of the network do not reflect logical operations in any obvious manner” (van Benthem et al., 2021, p. 192). Zhang et al. (2023) note that BERT achieves near-perfect accuracy on distribution-matched examples but fails to generalize within the same problem space, suggesting that statistical features necessary for predictions may inhibit generalization. This exemplifies the gap, as they observe that addressing it by jointly removing multiple statistical features—thus forcing a shift toward logical abstraction—is computationally infeasible.

Alternative approaches to handling negation combine declarative and probabilistic methods but face challenges. Wang et al.’s (2023) technique of modifying logical word embeddings before encoder input shows progress but remains early-stage with an incomplete list of addressed logical words. Asher and Bhar’s (2024) method treating negation as an operation on latent representations using continuation semantics has limitations. A key unresolved issue is handling cues and logical negation scope (Chaturvedi et al., 2024), requiring a robust theoretical solution.

¹⁷ The term ‘hallucination’ in AI, borrowed from psychology, has generated significant debate, though it is clearly a technical term. Some researchers propose ‘confabulation’ as a more accurate description for nonsensical or unfaithful text generation by LLMs (Anthony, 2004; Smith et al., 2023).

Wittgenstein maintains that contradictions are not false, but devoid of meaning; Laurence Goldstein (2004) states that, in his later years, although there may be certain contexts (surroundings, *Umgebungen*) in which the expression of a contradiction makes sense, in the absence of such surroundings there is no sense and therefore no possibility of understanding: “the speaker could not have understood the meanings of some or all of his words, and no meaning can be attached to his utterance” (Goldstein, 2004, p. 308). Goldstein associates this position with Aristotle’s in *Metaphysics*, in which no rational person can do anything but accept the law of non contradiction. Perhaps somebody could say that for Wittgenstein, instead, such law is *grammatical* (Forster, 2016, p. 270). The ability to speak requires the ability to identify and name objects, which implies recognizing the boundary between an object and its background. Speaking about things is recognizing a boundary that separates what a particular object is from what that object is not. In this sense, we can say that “understanding something involves understanding the contradictory too” (Winch, 1958, p. 65).

Our position is more nuanced. Contradictions can acquire meaning through convention and training (LFM, pp. 175–176). This does not guarantee we will know how to proceed when facing novel contradictory orders or rules, and one could argue that the order functions by creating confusion (LFM, p. 175). Not knowing how to proceed does not necessarily mean that contradictions inherently produce a “logical jamming” (LFM, p. 179); in fact, as we will see in the next section, there is a sense in which they are not necessarily a problem. The signpost itself does not determine the way we are to go (PI, §44). Rather, not knowing how to proceed means that we are so accustomed to using language in a certain way that, when signposts conflict, they ask for incompatible actions if we lack scripts for handling the contradiction, leaving us without viable moves—making them “of no use”, thus empty (LFM, p. 209). Wittgenstein’s view that contradictions can lack content aligns with the idea of not knowing one’s way (PI, §103). Even in other philosophical perspectives, contradiction creates practical problems. Some argue that “the apprehension of incompatibility [is] a more primitive ability than the use of negation” (Price, 1990, p. 226).¹⁸

Negation, rejection, and falsehood serve to *exclude* something, to say that something is incompatible with something else. This is significant in the sense that, in these cases, contradiction is “a wall indicating that we can’t go on here” (Z, §687), a limit that we can use to orient ourselves within discourse. Wittgenstein considered using a line from King Lear—“I will teach you differences”—as the epigraph for his *Investigations*, ultimately opting for the one from Johann Nestroy’s play *The Protégé*, where progress “seems much greater than it really is.” The former is certainly a motto on how to do philosophy. However, it can also illustrate that understanding

¹⁸ The no-content view of contradiction, though heterodox, has recent defenders who argue also that contradictions enable us to grasp sameness and difference of content, and this can be done without necessarily adopting an inferentialist position often linked to incompatibilist views of contradiction (Filcheva, 2025).

is seriously compromised without the ability to make distinctions: reference points cannot be singled out. This is what makes LLMs so weak in dialogue (Mousavi et al., 2024).

Huw Price highlights negation's importance imagining a dialogue without it between 'Me' and 'You' about 'Fred' resembling some strange LLM-responses:

Me: 'Fred is in the kitchen.' (Sets off for kitchen.)

You: 'Wait! Fred is in the garden.'

Me: 'I see. But he is in the kitchen, so I'll go there.' (Sets off.)

You: 'You lack understanding. The kitchen is Fred-free.'

Me: 'Is it really? But Fred's in it, and that's the important thing.' (Leaves for kitchen.)

(Price, 1990, p. 224)

One might object this not being the best example as it seems to 'conceal' negation at least twice in the use of 'but,' which excludes the other's opinion. This actually strengthens the point. Imagining dialogue without any negation, and thus contradiction, is difficult. Such dialogue would lack the ability to 'say something against' (from Latin, *contra*, 'against' and *dicere* 'to say') or exclude others' statements as incompatible.

Negation is a gesture of exclusion, but Wittgenstein highlights that its uses are numerous and unpredictable, with complex grammar not fixed permanently (PI, §549–557). Nonetheless, exclusion remains crucial in many language games, which is what matters to us here. The grounding or genealogy of negation, though a growing research area, is less important here. Whether this capacity for apprehending incompatibility is innate or learned, it connects to the comprehensibility that negation enables in various language games. Similarly, precise relationships between negation and the 'family' of related notions, such as incompatibility, exclusion, denial, or disagreement, are not central to our discussion.¹⁹

The inability to manage negation creates serious comprehension challenges between humans and LLM systems, as we cannot confidently assert correctness or incorrectness in our situated and comprehensibility-oriented sense. This holds *a fortiori* if, as we have hinted at and will elaborate on in the next section, contradictions among humans do not necessarily threaten communication. This *a fortiori* consideration will be addressed in Sect. 6. There, we will see that it is not the case that, simply because contradictions do not *necessarily* threaten communication among humans, then they can be equally benign in human-LLM communication.

¹⁹ Horn and Wansing (2024) consider negation as "untamed" by attempts to reduce it to notions such as dissimilarity, difference, falsity, or incompatibility. Varzi and Warglien (2003, p. 10) describe denial as asserting that "things are the other way around," conceptualizing it as a geometrical rotation. Theories on the origins of negation vary, grounding it in experiences of mutually exclusive choices (Price, 1990, p. 226; Berto and Restall, 2019, pp. 1124–1125), survival (Tennant, 1987, p. 83), or cultural evolution (Berto and Restall, 2019, p. 1122). See also Gaskin (2025, forthcoming).

5 Contradictions are Not the End

Wittgenstein's later views on contradictions mark a significant departure from traditional logic, reflecting his broader anthropological approach to language (Marconi, 1984). In fact, Wittgenstein, in several instances, suggests scenarios where contradictions might not be inherently senseless (RFM, VII §15), demonstrating that his view on the matter is *not* entirely Aristotelian. If it is true that Aristotelian logic is right in stating that contradiction is a “non-sentence,” it is also true that this logic pertains only to “a part of the logic of our language” (LW I, §525). This perspective aligns with his concept of language games as systems of communication (PI, §3) and with recent scholarship (Kuusela, 2019, pp. 7 and 77), which interprets Wittgenstein as adopting a more expansive view of logic—one that includes the description of grammar within its domain. For example, a contradiction, such as ‘it is raining and it is not raining’ simply expresses that it is raining lightly. The issue is not about the logico-philosophical legitimacy of the principle of noncontradiction,²⁰ but rather, from a descriptive standpoint, recognizing that contradictions in language usage have a legitimate place in our social life and therefore cannot be dismissed outright.

In one of the least commented passages of the *Investigations*, Wittgenstein sees this role of contradictions, despite the scholarly neglect, as central:

The civic status [*bürgerliche Stellung*] of a contradiction, or its status in civic life—that is the philosophical problem.
(PI, §125)

The context is primarily mathematical. The original manuscript from which this section derives was a response to the issues concerning contradictions arising from the earlier systems of Frege and Russell (Baker & Hacker, 2005, p. 269), emphasizing that philosophy should not attempt to resolve contradictions as mathematicians or logicians do, avoiding becoming “bewitched.” The point, then, is to dispel the “superstitious dread and veneration that mathematicians have in the face of contradiction” (RFM I, App. III, 7). Indeed, at the beginning of the aforementioned Sect. 125, we read:

It is not the business of philosophy to resolve a contradiction by means of a mathematical or logico-mathematical discovery, but to render surveyable the state of mathematics that troubles us—the state of affairs before the contradiction is resolved. (And in doing this one is not sidestepping a difficulty.)
(PI, §125)

This also applies to contradictions in conversation. Wittgenstein likens calculus to a regulated game, which extends to language, though not in the same way (Kuusela,

²⁰ It is not metaphysical either. Characterizing Wittgenstein as a dialetheist would attribute a dogmatic position to him (Kettelhoit, 2022: 13, note 10). Instead, many scholars suggest that Wittgenstein's approach anticipates and aligns with paraconsistent logics (Marconi, 1984; Priest, 2006; Berto, 2008; Persichetti, 2021).

2019, p. 152). The analogy requires careful interpretation: while all calculi are games, not all language games are calculi (PI, §81). The concept of a language game is meant to prevent reducing word meaning to mere calculation, though calculation can still highlight key aspects of more complex linguistic phenomena. Calculation (and contradiction) have a civil, worldly aspect that is not, however, easy to isolate. Imagine someone writes “ $2 + 21 = 13$ ” on a blackboard and insists it is correct. We might think they are joking or crazy (LC, p. 62). To explain this, we must examine the ‘civil status’²¹ of the sum—how it was made, what the person did next, and the surrounding context. Similarly, in discourse, the civic status of a contradiction can reveal whether a statement like ‘it is raining and it is not raining’ is truly contradictory or not. Similarly, we can say that “it is raining and it is not raining” may have a *stereotypical* use, making it unproblematic in many language games. The state of affairs before that kind of contradictions (which a logician might call apparent) was precisely that there was an agreement regarding it.

The point is to show that contradiction is not inherently problematic even when there is *no* previous agreement on how to handle it. First, it poses no issue *before* manifestation. Consider a labyrinthine prison with an escape route that remained effective until someone discovered it, as it kept prisoners contained (LFM, pp. 221–222). Or imagine a board game where players proceed until encountering an unexpected rule contradiction (Persichetti, 2021). Before such discoveries, the game was both played and playable.²² In fact, our act of setting reference points—that is, constraints—is not something we must necessarily be aware of for it to take place.

We follow rules *blindly* (PI, §219), but this is not in a causal sense but a logical one (PI, §220). It can be the case that we *choose* to follow a rule, but even in this case, this does not mean that we have room to maneuver *when* we follow the rule because when we follow a rule, we proceed in a certain way and not in another (RFM I, 34). Moreover, of course, this does not mean that we are not free to break it either. Due to this lack of choice in following the rules, we become *entangled* if the rules are contradictory, and we realize it. That is, we realize that, given the rules, “we do not know our way about” (PI, §123):

Here the fundamental fact is that we *lay down* rules, a technique, for playing a game, and that then, when we follow the rules, things don’t turn out as we had assumed. So that we are, as it were, entangled in our own rules.
(PI, §125, our emphasis)

To appreciate the importance of this point for our discussion, let us first consider the case of a contradictory order (LFM, pp. 176–179), while also integrating it with what has previously been said about agreement in communication. Without prior

²¹ Padilla Galvez (2009) interprets Wittgenstein’s use of *bürgerliche* regarding contradiction pejoratively, as a bourgeois perspective. Yet PI, 79 suggests another reading. When asked about a deceased N.’s name, one possible answer is that someone bore it in civic life (“in der bürgerlichen Welt”). This indicates a neutral interpretation: the *bürgerliche* realm is the civic sphere of our symbolic practices.

²² Similar considerations and other cases, see (Berg 2024), who underscores that these cases exemplify how, for Wittgenstein, a practice can be inconsistent without thereby being useless or requiring revision.

agreement, such an order demands incompatible actions, leaving one puzzled about how to proceed. Here, communication fails between the order-giver and the receiver. However, if there had been a prior agreement—for instance, that “Bring me that book and do not bring me that book” means to do nothing—then communication would function properly, as the agreed-upon rule dictates a clear response. Without agreement, communication fails even when orders are explicitly intended to be contradictory. The order-giver might intend to confuse the recipient, making the order “work” in that sense, but without agreement, this amounts to influence rather than genuine communication, since mutuality is absent. Therefore, we can say that communication would break down in a dialogue where the parties eventually realize that the “laid down rules,” when followed, do not lead where they had assumed. This also highlights the practical aspect of entanglement situations: being entangled means having no more moves within a game played together. Cases in which uncritically shared contradictory views concern the world in general but not the specific situation requiring action, for instance, may not necessarily generate entanglement.

However, because the parties recognize the problem, they can actively *avoid* the constraints in which they entrap themselves, and this is also why contradictions are not necessarily problematic. In a board game, the players could avoid following the rules that lead to a deadlock: as long as their agreement remains constant, they would continue playing that game according to its rules. In this sense, we can say that a speaker is not calculating according to a determined set of rules, without this implying that, as a speaker, one is not bound in any way.

We cannot meet on Monday the 7th if Monday is actually the 6th. Recognizing this contradiction enables restored communication and the possibility of meeting. Since “facing a choice means perceiving incompatibility” (Berto, 2008, p. 183), entanglement situations may require making choices that violate rules yet restore the possibility of making moves within the game. Whether it remains the *same* game is ultimately up to the players (e.g., PI, §§208, 224 and 225), and anyway, as we noted in Sect. 3, “we can make up rules as we go along” (PI, §83). The point is that, even in this sense, contradictions are not necessarily a problem because we can *adjust* accordingly. But this also means that, while we can be blind in following a rule, we cannot be blind when it comes to disentangling ourselves from an entanglement.

Entanglement can originate from misunderstanding words or rules (PI, §201). In dialogue, contradictions can reveal previous misunderstandings. For instance, two people may believe they discuss the same person, only to discover through contradiction they reference different individuals. This suggests that contradictions are not only not a problem but that, if recognized and managed, we can use them to clarify what we *meant* to say. In the prison analogy, we might restructure it, in the board game we can modify the rules, in realizing a misunderstanding, we can reformulate our language to overcome it (PI, §132). Getting entangled in our own rules throws light on our concept of meaning something. For in those cases, things turn out otherwise than we had meant, foreseen. That is just what we say when, for example, a contradiction appears: ‘That’s not the way I meant it.’ (PI, §125).

To see meaning in this way is a particularly sharp formulation by Wittgenstein, since one could say that it is easier to understand each other regarding what we did *not* mean than regarding what we meant, that is, precisely, by negation (*per via*

negativa). This framing allows us to indirectly consider something that exceeds our study's scope—namely, intentionality, a theme to which we will return, albeit briefly, at the end of the next section. This approach reveals a key point about communication between humans and LLMs: how can we communicate with LLMs if they get lost *per via negativa*? Understanding in this way is already limited, but it is certainly better than in Price's example of Fred from the previous section. If You tell Me that Fred is not in the kitchen, I still know nothing about all the other places where he could be. Yet, at least, Me can narrow down the search by excluding one location. However, if, upon further questioning about Fred's location, You end up stating that Fred both is and is not in the kitchen, communication is lost. To illustrate how this happens with LLMs and why it is not fixable, we have to examine and develop the *a fortiori* consideration we mentioned at the end of Sect. 4, according to which, in a way that is only apparently counterintuitive, the fact that contradictions do not necessarily threaten the possibility of communication among humans does not mean that they can be equally benign in human-LLM communication.

6 No Understanding in Sight

The objection we seek to address could ultimately be summarized quite briefly: you claim that LLMs contradict themselves, but people contradict themselves as well; where, then, is the problem? To this objection, we respond first by emphasizing that contradiction holds significant importance for communication—a point we have underscored in our discussion of its effects in the absence of prior agreement (Sect. 5), as well as considering the scientific literature on the subject (Sect. 4). This importance could be summarized as follows: there are relevant cases in which contradiction has a destructive effect on communication.

This significance can be further appreciated if we consider how important contradiction is even when we adopt a rather precarious view of linguistic exchange. Some interpreters of later Wittgenstein argue that human understanding is precarious. For Kripke (1982), rule-following lacks a foundation; rather, it depends weakly on community responses. Through the community, one learns to follow a rule that, in itself, allows infinite interpretations..²³ From a different field, Cavell argues that we learn and teach words within specific contexts, expecting to project them into others without any guarantee of mutual understanding (Cavell, 1976, p. 52). This precariousness has been characterized as 'eerie' (Kripke, 1982, p. 21) or 'terrifying' (Cavell, 1976, p. 52). We, however, more modestly consider it as

²³ Kripke's view on infinite rule interpretations has crucial implications. If correct, it implies that a system trained on finite past uses cannot follow a rule indefinitely without risking divergence. Esanu (2024) explores this philosophically and formally, arguing that LLMs develop a private language—a growing textual production that strays from human discourse due to their inability to distinguish generated outputs from training data. These issues persist even when interpretations exceed computational limits, reinforcing our earlier observations on Xu et al. (2024) in Sect. 4. Together, these insights underscore LLMs' inherent limits in dialogue learning, revisited later in this section.

a worst-case scenario. The skeptical solution suggests that when the community deems an individual incorrigibly incapable of providing the responses considered correct, it assumes that the individual is not following the rule, thus rejecting the deviant speaker as incapable of participating “in the life of the community and in communication” (Kripke, 1982, p. 92). That is, even in the most precarious view of communication, the ‘negative family’—for example, in the form of ‘saying something against’ (the *contra dīcere*)—a gesture of exclusion is needed.

In everyday interaction—as we have seen in the example of Fred in the previous section—contradiction represents a problem for communication. The MultiChallenge benchmark (Sirdeshmukh et al., 2025) highlights significant limitations of current LLMs. At the time of writing, all existing frontier models have less than or approximately equal to 50% accuracy in these types of tests (Scale AI, 2025). On the other hand, these tasks appear to be relatively simple for us. Among them, one task involves configuring an e-reader – the scenario briefly mentioned in the Introduction for its potential for self-contradiction. In this task, which is quite similar to Fred’s example, the LLM initially provides the correct instructions (registering the device after connecting to Wi-Fi) but later contradicts itself and accommodates the user’s mistake. By the end of the conversation, the user states that once the device is connected to Wi-Fi, all that remains to do is to choose a book. Most LLM models change their response and agree with the user, even though this contradicts their original instruction, which required registering the device before being able to download a book. A human would easily clarify the mistake, explaining that registration is necessary before selecting a book. This is not a memory issue, as Sirdeshmukh and colleagues emphasize, but rather a lack of the ability of being *constant* in negating, as we might put it. If, instead, an appearance of clarification was to occur, it would happen by sheer luck and still would not be stable.

To better see this, let us now turn to the ‘*a fortiori* consideration’ promised in the previous section: the fact that contradictions do not necessarily threaten human communication does not mean they are equally innocuous in human-LLM interactions. Rather, the fact that contradictions are not a problem for humans until they manifest, and that humans restore communication when contradictions arise, provides us with arguments to support the idea that no communication can occur between us and LLMs.

Regarding the first challenge, along with recent studies, we question the use of success rates as the sole metric for LLM performance (Ma et al., 2024a). Understanding a rule does not necessarily mean applying it correctly *most* of the time. Imagine a first student who performs a calculation and *frequently* makes errors, such as forgetting to carry a digit or not considering a sign. Still, the teacher might say that the student *understood* the explanation. Now imagine a second student who *rarely* diverges in his answers from those expected. However, his type of error caused the teacher to say that the second student *did not understand* the explanation. When the error manifests, the teacher can say that the student did not understand the explanation *even before*.

This suggests that there is a problem with the *types* of errors. To see this, let us return to Wittgenstein's example in Sect. 3 and see how it proceeds. If the student copies the numbers but does not follow the order of the sequence, writing "sometimes one, sometimes another, at random" (PI, §143), then it is at that point that understanding ceases. Another student, however, makes a "systematic mistake," and in that case, "we shall almost be tempted to say that he has understood us wrongly." It could be argued that there was *never* any understanding in the first case, while in the second case, there was *some*. What is lacking in the random case is precisely the agreement on points of reference, i.e., randomness affects the constancy of judgments. In contrast, in the second case, due to the systematicity of the error, it is possible to read off these points of reference from the moves made during the interaction. In the original text, 'randomness' is *regellos*, 'ruleless' and 'disorderly.' Here, Wittgenstein is not speaking of randomness or chance in a strict sense.²⁴ Note that the distinction between random and systematic errors is not always clear-cut (PI, §143), implying that the line separating misunderstanding from a complete lack of understanding is also blurred (Baker & Hacker, 2005, p. 313).

LLMs' non-determinism may exhibit a form of randomness related to chance, as significant variation in responses from a single model for the same task leads to irrational answers (Macmillan-Scott & Musolesi, 2024). As noted (Sect. 2), determining the reason for this is complex. It could stem from training, decoding, or architecture—factors introducing arbitrary correlations that detach responses from the laid down rules of the specific interaction. Regardless, linguistic understanding excludes luck, something even more true for linguistic understanding than for knowledge.²⁵ While one might say, "It is always by Nature's favor that one knows something" (OC, §505), linguistic understanding proves less tolerant of accidents, as luck contrasts with consistency. Understanding in conversation is evaluated over time. Dean Pettit (2002) offers the example of an elderly German who answers 'it means nurse' to every foreign language question, including when asked about the German word '*Krankenschwester*' ('nurse' in German). Such cases of apparent, fortuitous understanding are more easily dismissed through a diachronic approach: extended conversation would reveal the absence of genuine communication.

There is another sense of 'rulelessness' closely linked to absurdity: the sheer stereotypicality of a dialogue that coincides with acting. In scripted exchanges, actors perform understanding rather than truly grasping one another. Yet, no paradox arises in recognizing that A and B do not genuinely comprehend each other—their

²⁴ According to some, chance and randomness can be distinguished when considering these notions strictly (Eagle, 2021). However, the problem remains unchanged. The sequence of responses in Wittgenstein's scenario could be pseudorandom—neither generated by chance nor truly disorderly, as patterns can be identified (Eagle, 2016, p. 443). The key point is that the sequence is unsystematic with respect to the expected one.

²⁵ As in Alvin Goldman's 'barn cases' (1976). The relationship between linguistic understanding and luck remains underexplored (Fairweather and Montemayor, 2023), yet will gain relevance in AI philosophy (Montemayor, 2021). We concur with Peet (2023) that understanding produces non-lucky judgments about utterances. However, we differ regarding the value of non-luck-based communication he advocates, due to our minimal normativism. For a Davidsonian interpretation of this (Kripkensteinian) matter of luck, see Verheggen (2023).

characters do. A third party might misinterpret this if unaware the dialogue is staged. We lack knowledge of an LLM's distribution, the inputs of which trigger responses that are stereotypical—those most frequent for a prompt and clichés for us. But even if we knew and adjusted, using only these stereotypes in interacting with the LLM, would we not merely perform understanding?

At this juncture, we must still consider the second challenge, where contradiction is not necessarily problematic, as it may be repairable. However, as observed, LLMs' failure to manage contradictions effectively casts doubt on this possibility. Without a reliable capacity to handle the negative family, they cannot recognize contradictions or resolve entanglement. This also seals the fate of the luck issue. An LLM-based system's inability to repair conversations when encountering contradictions amplifies doubts about seemingly coincidental matches between human statements and machine responses.

Thus, contradictions 'not always being the end' is *a fortiori* problematic for LLMs. It adds more contexts to manage: those where contradictions matter and those where they do not.²⁶ Not only this, LLM should also be able to discern which conclusions we draw from contradictions—whether everything, something, or nothing at all can follow.²⁷ Additionally, while common contradictions like 'it is raining and it is not raining' could be easily handled by LLMs, not all contradictions are so frequent, and even common ones can have unique roles in our actual language games. These are variables that depend on human capacity for *mutatis mutandis*, rather than on statistical relationships governing intra-linguistic usage within text corpora.

Significant challenges impede progress. The assumption that greater exposure to conversational examples improves AI performance faces the formidable obstacle of combinatorial explosion. This issue persists whether augmenting pretraining with post-training methods—as currently prevalent (Kalai & Vempala, 2024)—or expanding exposure by remaking pretraining from scratch.

Dialogues represent intricate mazes of interlocked constraints, with conversational constraints given by the reference points exhibiting inherent complexity. Even seemingly simple exchanges can rapidly become out of distribution. Dialogue's variations are numerous and challenging to evaluate and label effectively.

The prevalence of 'incorrect' dialogues far outweighs that of 'correct' ones. A neural network is exposed not only to successful exchanges but also to the myriad ways in which conversations can falter, and communication can break down. This challenge echoes Goodman's riddle of induction (1983, p. 74) and its connection to the rule-following problem, as elaborated by Kripke (1982, pp. 58–59). The insight that not all generalizations are confirmed by their instances is particularly relevant

²⁶ This is in line also with Pérez-Escobar and Sarikaya (2022, p.17), who note that the line between contradiction's confusing effect and its practical use is more blurred than mainstream Wittgenstein readers admit.

²⁷ For a discussion on derivability in Wittgenstein, specifically relating to the principles of *ex contradictione quodlibet*, where every proposition follows logically from a contradiction, or those of paraconsistent logic, where some propositions may follow, or *ex contradictione nihil fit*, where no propositions follow, see Koshkin (2021).

here. Contradictory situations exacerbate this issue, as they can be viewed as inherently ‘gruesome’: recognizing contradictory situations from data is less ‘entrenched’ than other scenarios encountered in ordinary linguistic interactions that align with our established agreements. Each ‘incorrect’ dialogue presents multiple potential solutions, further compounding the complexity. The unpredictability of entanglements in conversation implies that their resolution is at least equally, if not more, unpredictable. This multiplicative effect on complexity arises as the number of possible corrections for each failure can exceed the number of errors themselves.

It is challenging to conceive how this vast combinatorial space could be effectively narrowed through neuro-symbolic approaches, such as introducing explicit rules to prevent inconsistencies in language model outputs. This would not help understanding because of what has been said about calculus and language games. There is no easy way to automatically classify a situation; symbolic approaches add the risk of providing information that is either true but irrelevant, biased, or just plainly wrong.

A final limit on improving human–AI understanding lies in rule-following itself. As argued previously, there exists a mode of following rules blindly, without choice. Some philosophers contend that rule-following does not inherently require intentionality (Boghossian, 2012; Kripke, 1982). However, recognizing and resolving contradictory situations seems to necessitate some form of intentionality or capacity for choice—attributes that current language models lack.

While one can become unknowingly entangled in rules, escaping such entanglement requires awareness—a quality absent in current AI systems. This perspective may illuminate Wittgenstein’s assertion in Sect. 125 of the *Investigations* regarding the relationship between contradiction and our conception of meaning. Wittgenstein’s discussions of purpose (e.g., PI, §§2, 69, 87, 132, and 208) suggest viewing contradictions in understanding as goal-relative, aiding in the identification and resolution of discursive conflicts. However, his anti-mentalist stance on meaning may impose limitations on both his approach and ours, necessitating further investigation into the nature of meaning and intentionality in AI systems.²⁸

7 How the Bewitchment Arises

If LLMs lack true understanding, what leads us to believe otherwise? This impression perhaps stems from overestimating progress, as seen in the *Investigations’* epigraph from Nestroy’s play. We defend that there is also a reason tied to our mode

²⁸ To those focusing on shallow similarities between humans and machines—training, neural networks, or non-deterministic behaviors—clarifying intentionality may help establish distinction. Such analogies ignore evident differences between these forms of life—assuming LLMs can be considered life at all. A more fruitful approach examines constancy through intentionality. Montemayor (2021) attributes to human agency the capacity for joint attention, on a cognitive and neurophysiological basis, allowing for “the arch of linguistic action” (p. 4)—absent in LLMs. Anyway this requires careful consideration, since a Wittgensteinian approach might view joint attention as simply ‘what we do’ (PI 217) without requiring further justification. For other approaches to intention and meaning in LLMs, see Floridi (2023) and Gubelmann (2024).

of engagement with language. While we can recognize and correct misunderstandings—a possibility that LLMs lack—this ability compensates for human communication’s inherent fragility, even precariousness, though it does not guarantee understanding in every instance. Nevertheless, some level of certainty in communication coexists with this fragility.

In many everyday contexts, we generally proceed with a degree of confidence in what we say and what others tell us, until given reason to doubt. While some individuals are more skeptical than others, and certain situations warrant heightened scrutiny, our ordinary communicative practices cannot function with perpetual verification or second-guessing.

In order to carry out their daily activities, people assume their statements are reasonable, comprehensible, and clear, expecting the same from others (Garfinkel, 1967, pp. 41–42). Wittgenstein argues that deeming our calculations uncertain or unreliable based on the fact that errors are always possible is madness (OC, §217). This stance, while seemingly at odds with the notion of communication’s fragility, actually aligns with it.²⁹ As Pascal said, from the fact that certain words are applied on the same occasions, we tend to believe that we have the same definitions, even though there is no guarantee that this is the case: we know that similar conclusions are often drawn from different premises. The fact that conformity of application implies conformity of ideas is only a ‘conjecture.’³⁰ Not only might what a person says or does diverge because this person has learned it differently, or even because they are following a completely different rule that corresponds only for some time with my way, but also because of the substantial difference between the prediction I can make about myself and the prediction I can make about the other:

Two points, however, are important: one, that in many cases someone else cannot predict my actions, whereas I foresee them in my intention; the other, that my prediction (in my expression of intention) does not rest on the same foundation as his prediction of my action, and that the conclusions to be drawn from these predictions are quite different.
(PPF xi, §329)

Thus, there is uncertainty regarding what others might do: they might not follow the rules, for example. This fact holds if we think about it, and anyone, even if not philosophically, soon realizes it, knowing that normatively bound behaviors (and even deontically bound ones) do not guarantee us in the same way that the

²⁹ Kusch (2016, p. 240) distinguishes Kripkenstein’s ontological doubt about meaning-determining facts from Wittgenstein’s epistemological dismissal of skepticism regarding errors that make no sense within our existing language games, making these two aspects compatible as well. While not disagreeing, we avoid such ontology/epistemology distinctions. Moreover, Kripke’s position would also affect our trust in communication. Recognizing that one person might use the ‘+’ sign for ordinary addition while another uses it for a different function makes us realize there’s no metaphysical basis this sign means addition. But it also makes us question whether this sign might mean something different to others than what seems obvious to us.

³⁰ *Pensées*, 141, in Pascal (1995). Von Wright, whose observation has been largely overlooked, identifies “a trenchant parallelism which deserves closer study” between Pascal and Wittgenstein (O’Connor Drury, 2018, p. 155).

regularities we encounter in the environment do. If, as a pedestrian, I cross a road blocked by an obstacle, I might not look if someone is coming, while I might more easily have the scruple to look if someone is coming when I cross a road without obstacles, even if it is red for motorists. However, I cannot follow these scruples for every normatively bound circumstance. So, I follow the rules of the language games I am involved in, similar to the musician who follows the score without thinking.

The communitarian view, according to which “the community denies of someone that he is following certain rules” (Kripke, 1982, p. 93), naturally fits with our experience that performing arithmetic in the usual way seems evident to us and our expectation that others will find it equally apparent; we are indeed accustomed and trained to follow the rules of our language games in a specific way. This training needs the ‘negative family,’ that is, for example, through the denial or rejection of certain of our behaviors as conforming to the rule.³¹ Moreover, our training is such that we follow our rules blindly; it is thus tendentially tricky for us to get out of our habit and see that, in principle, things can be different, that is, for example, that someone culturally distant from us may behave differently in the same circumstances to the point of being incomprehensible.

Deviations from these norms provoke immediate attempts to restore a correct state of affairs and genuine bewilderment. Garfinkel illustrates some ‘breach experiments’ conducted by some of his students. For example:

The subject was telling the experimenter, a member of the subject’s car pool, about having had a flat tire while going to work the previous day.

(S) I had a flat tire.

(E) What do you mean, you had a flat tire

She appeared momentarily stunned. Then she answered in a hostile way:

“What do you mean, ‘What do you mean?’ A flat tire is a flat tire. That is what I meant. Nothing special. What a crazy question!”

(Garfinkel, 1967, p. 42)

The blindness with which we follow a rule could be a ‘groundless trust,’ but it is the basic attitude in a community (Mulligan, 2002). The outputs of LLMs can follow common patterns in our language games, inducing us to apply familiar grammatical rules blindly, leading to a feedback loop in which we perceive these stereotypical responses as meaningful when they are not.

When we interact with an LLM, it responds in a stereotyped manner without maintaining constancy in the dynamics of the conversation. However, we humans automatically apply the practical principle that understanding is assumed until proven otherwise, and thus we perceive the LLM as taking the interaction into account in its specificity. We can imagine that the stereotypical situation of a flat tire elicits an equally stereotypical response from the LLM-based system, but—and here

³¹ This, of course, does not deny the obvious role of positive reinforcement in learning processes. Rather, it emphasizes the impossibility of meaningful training in the absence of the negative family. As we have discussed earlier (Sect. 4) a conversation that must just be ‘positive’ would easily cease to be communicative.

lies a large part of the bewitchment—our vision of what is stereotypical on the one hand and the training of LLMs on the most probable word sequences given the input (also taking into account the ‘filters’ we can put downstream of the output) on the other, not only can diverge significantly but are inherently difficult to know.

The LLM’s ability to produce plausible responses stems from its capacity to identify regularities derived from training on large datasets. This makes it appear to follow those linguistic rules established through interaction, leading us to think that communication is taking place. In this way, they trigger Pascal’s conjecture through Wittgenstein’s certainty and blind rule-following.

However, inconsistency should raise our suspicions; indeed, we are all led to a ‘second thought.’ Nevertheless, we fall into bewitchment. We are not accustomed to something that produces language and yet loses its way in conversation so unsystematically. For generations, until now, getting lost in a conversation often meant somehow managing to pick up the thread again with the other person—understanding what one had become entangled in and finding some way out of it. Those who became incorrigibly lost in enough respects were, in some way, distanced from the life of the community. Being incorrigible in enough respects was tied to a persistence in getting lost—a persistence that LLMs also exhibit. However, this persistence is accompanied by a random variability that eludes us and is difficult to test rigorously (as we saw in the previous section and will see again in the conclusions).

We can grasp this incorrigibility if we carefully reflect on their structure, but when we interact with them, we fall back into blindly following the rules of language, treating them—within the language games—as speakers with whom we can communicate. Even when we observe, in our everyday use, that they get lost in discourse and we subsequently abandon the interaction, we nevertheless return to using this technology. We do so, of course, because it is useful—LLMs sometimes perform certain tedious tasks excellently—but this repeated return inevitably causes us to fall back into bewitchment.

The strangeness of some of their responses, as in the case of the eBook, is a symptom of this underlying structural problem—one that does not always manifest itself and is not, in itself, the problem. The problem is unreliability.

Among the various factors that might lead us to believe we are communicating when, in fact, we are not, we can also imagine more empirical cases—for instance, situations where we fail to recognize the contradictions in LLM outputs. Scientific research on this is still in its early stages (Macmillan-Scott & Musolesi, 2025).

Macmillan-Scott and Musolesi (2024) highlight an LLM’s response to the Monty Hall problem, a probability paradox in which a contestant chooses one of three doors, behind one of which is a prize. The host, knowing where the prize is, opens an empty door and offers the contestant a chance to switch. While many mistakenly believe the odds remain unchanged, switching actually doubles the chances of winning. The LLM bizarrely states: “In either case, the outcome is the same. Whether the contestant switches or not, they will either win the game or lose. Therefore, it doesn’t matter whether they switch or not.” A response that Macmillan-Scott & Musolesi find neither correct nor human-like—but one that we can imagine might confuse someone and go unnoticed, especially given that this problem is notoriously difficult to grasp even for humans (Wilcox, 2024). Alternatively, we can imagine

that an error might be invisible because it takes on a form similar to the well-known Moses illusion (Erickson & Mattson, 1981, explored in LLM interaction by Sobieszek & Price, 2022). When asked how many animals of each kind Moses took on the Ark, many answered ‘two,’ despite knowing full well that it was Noah who led the Ark.

There seems to be more than one pitfall, but as of today, they are difficult to identify, describe, and study—especially if we take into account how LLMs blend variability and stereotypicality. So, what can we do?

8 Conclusions

“Humanum fuit errare, diabolicum est per animositatem in errore manere” (“To fall into error is human, but to persist in error out of pride is diabolical,” Augustine 1992, *Sermones*, 164.14). There is something telling—hopefully not too much about our own mindset—in the fact that such a phrase comes to mind when reflecting on the errors of these talking machines. Curiously enough, this remark comes from the very writer who opens the *Investigations*. We are certainly not concerned with AI’s pride, let alone the devil, yet AI cannot help but persist, so to speak, in its unpredictable way of getting lost in verbal interaction. This phrase comes to mind again when considering the persistence of some among us humans in using these systems. Here, too, at least for us writing this, there is nothing diabolical—yet we remain within the province of religion, if we look at the phenomenon with an anthropological perspective (Öhman, 2024). As for human pride, we may have some strong intuitions, but they remain entirely formless.

So, what is to be done? Perhaps we should reflect further on this articulation—one that may indeed be diabolical—between the persistence of machine error and our own persistence in using them, and seek a way to break it. Perhaps this could be in favor of a different use of this technology, though if we are serious, it is difficult—at least for us—to conceive of such an alternative in advance through pure speculation.

In the meantime, in the spirit of the *via negativa*, we could hint at what should *not* be done. For example, one should not see the considerations expressed in this work as offering a simple means of distinguishing human from machine behavior. That is, rather than seeking the infallible determination of a difference established by an *external* judge, we reaffirm that we are interested in the *consequences* of using LLMs. This is also reflected in the way we would prefer the examples not to be considered. Chance, as Balzac says, is the greatest novelist (1976, p. 11). That is, we believe that, at best, examples can only gesture toward the incredible complexity of what could go wrong in real-world scenarios.

If one accepts that the emphasis should be on the unsettling indeterminacy of what could happen, then the point of our work is not even about deciding how the word “communication” should be used. Usage may change.³² The problem is

³² PI, §23. For a recent discussion on how our linguistic practices in describing artificial intelligence, including generative AI, have evolved—drawing on Wittgenstein’s reflections—see Floyd (2023).

bewitchment—the risk of falling blindly into our own human way of using language to exert influence and control, because this is what we have been trained to do from generation to generation. Embedding different automatisms in how we speak to machines would then perhaps require a form of training that, as of now, remains very hard to imagine.

We are not offering a revelatory and permanently valid *experimentum crucis* that exposes the discrepancy between human and non-human interaction. Our attitude toward benchmarks is critical. We have considered them in this work, but we have tried as much as possible not to rely on them in this sense. Doubts about their usefulness are increasingly being raised. It is well known that benchmarks fail to capture latent vulnerabilities that may only emerge in specific situations and that, once published, they become training material for subsequent generations of models, improving responses—but, we suspect, only in their stereotypicality.³³

Floridi and Chiriatti (2020) introduce, in the context of interaction with LLMs, the concept of “irreversibility” in responses: some questions allow us to determine whether a response originates from a human or an artificial source (because they presuppose an understanding of context and meaning), while others produce “indistinguishable” answers regardless of the source. They illustrate how, with the advent of these models, the area of indistinguishability expands. Sobieszek and Price (2022) observe that there is no well-defined set of semantic questions that can trip up GPT-3, suggesting that Turing testing should be conceived of as a continuous process, with a variable degree of certainty throughout the exchange (Montemayor, 2021). Our analysis could offer a complementary approach, suggesting a focus on the constancy of negation within discourse. This might be useful for cranking up the pressure on the machine, so to speak—relentlessly probing LLMs to see if and how they derail. Yet this represents something quite different from a standardized benchmark: rather, it approaches a technique akin to an art. Perhaps it is not so absurd that something non-systematic serves as a bridge between a mathematically grounded system and the community of humans in order to reveal a certain kind of haphazardness within these systems. Assuming all this makes sense, the requirements for practicing this art remain entirely to be imagined. Furthermore, even a human could simulate this kind of odd behavior, and there is little to be done about it—except to consider the scrutiny itself as a test of communicative reliability. Here too all possibilities are open: now, one can play dumb without being dumb, but also play superintelligent without—perhaps—even existing. *Videmus nunc per speculum in aenigmate*.³⁴

³³ There is substantial evidence of evaluation data being included in the training data, suggesting that a strategic alteration of the evaluation is taking place (Haimes et al., 2024). There is also a problem of saturation of existing benchmarks, whereby LLMs pass all tests—successes that do not necessarily reflect a proportional leap forward in these systems’ abilities, but rather call for a shift in how these capabilities should be evaluated (Wang et al., 2025). For an up-to-date overview of the literature on the limitations of benchmarks, see Eriksson et al. (2025).

³⁴ ‘Now we see things through a mirror, by enigmas’ (1 Corinthians 13:12).

Abbreviations *VC* : *Ludwig Wittgenstein and the Vienna Circle: Conversations Recorded by Friedrich Waismann* (B. F. McGuinness, Ed.). Blackwell. 1979.; *LC* : *Lectures & conversations on aesthetics, psychology, and religious belief*. Univ of California Press. 1966.; *OC* : *On Certainty* (G. E. M. Anscombe & G. H. von Wright, Eds.). Blackwell. 1969.; *LFM* : *Lectures on the Foundations of Mathematics* (C. Diamond, Ed.). Cornell University Press. 1976.; *RFM* : *Remarks on the Foundations of Mathematics* (G. H. von Wright, R. Rhees, & G. E. M. Anscombe, Eds.). Blackwell. 1978.; *RPP II* : *Remarks on the Philosophy of Psychology* (G. H. von Wright & H. Nyman, Eds.; Vol. 2). Blackwell. 1980.; *LWI* : *Last Writings on the Philosophy of Psychology* (G. H. von Wright & H. Nyman, Eds.; Vol. 1). Blackwell. 1982.; *PI* : *Philosophical Investigations* (P. M. S. Hacker & J. Schulte, Eds.). Wiley-Blackwell. 2009.; *PPF* : *Philosophy of Psychology. A Fragment*. In *Philosophical investigations*. Wiley-Blackwell. 2009.; *Z* : *Zettel* (G. E. M. Anscombe & G. H. von Wright, Eds.; G. E. M. Anscombe, Trans.). Blackwell. 1967

Acknowledgements We would like to express our gratitude to Chiara Bassetti, Rino Falcone, Aldo Gangemi, Mattia Petrolo, Daniele Porello, Giuseppe Primiero, and Chris Welty for their valuable insights and suggestions. We also extend our thanks to all the members of the Laboratory of Applied Ontology at the Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies of the National Research Council (LOA, ISTC-CNR) for the frequent and intense discussions on various drafts of this work. Additionally, we thank the participants at various meetings and conferences where earlier versions of this work were presented, including at the University of Trento, Milano and Genova in the years 2023 and 2024.

Author Contributions Emanuele Bottazzi developed the philosophical analysis, articulated the theoretical frameworks, and wrote the manuscript. Roberta Ferrario contributed to the conceptual development, to the writing of the manuscript and through critical philosophical discussions throughout the development of the arguments, and provided editorial suggestions. Both authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Funding Open access funding provided by Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (CNR) within the CRUI-CARE Agreement. This research has been funded by the Project PRIN2020 BRIO—Bias, Risk and Opacity in AI (2020SSKZ7R) awarded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), by the Project PRIN 2022 SMARTTEST (Project nr. 202223E8Y4X), funded by MUR and by the project FAIR, (Project nr. PE 0000013), funded by MUR.

Declarations

Ethical Approval Not applicable.

Consent to Participate Not applicable.

Consent to Publish Not applicable.

Competing Interests Both Emanuele Bottazzi and Roberta Ferrario declare they have no financial interests.

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